

concentration and was complete at 0.03 *M* of the reagent. Lead was completely stripped back from chloroform layer into HNO₃ of different strengths (0.1–2.0 *N*). Hence, a 0.1 *N* HNO₃ solution was used as the stripping agent. Extraction was complete within 1 min, and 30 s was enough for back-extraction. To be on the safe side, 5 min was allowed to settle the equilibrium in both the cases.

Separation of lead from various ions : Lead was separated from binary, ternary and quaternary mixtures of known amounts of various ions (amount in parenthesis in μg); the results for the determination of 20 μg lead (within an error of $\pm 2\%$) are as follows: (i) binary mixtures: Na^I, K^I, Li^I (2000); Ca^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II} (800); Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II} (250); Mg^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} (200); Cu^{II}, Al^{III}, Ga^{III}, Cr^{III} (160); Ti^{IV}, VO₃⁻, MoO₄²⁻ (100); Fe^{II} (60); large amounts of F⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻ did not interfere; (ii) ternary and quaternary mixtures: (a) Ba^{II} (500) + Mn^{II} (200); (b) Ni^{II} (100) + Zn^{II} (100); (c) Al^{III} (100) + Cu^{II} (100); (d) Mg^{II} (100) + MoO₄²⁻ (50) + Fe^{II} (50); (e) Ca^{II} (500) + Cd^{II} (200) + VO₃⁻ (50); (f) Sr^{II} (500) + Cr^{III} (100) + Ti^{IV} (50).

Nature of the extracted species : To determine the composition of the extracted species extractions were carried out by keeping the concentration of lead constant and varying pH of the medium. The data were found to satisfy the linear relation⁴,

$$\log D = \log K_{\text{ex}} + (m+n) \log [\text{H(LCE)}]_0 + n\text{pH}$$

where, *D* = distribution ratio, *K_{ex}* = extraction constant, *m* = number of adduct molecule, *n* = number of chelating agent bound to metal and [H(LCE)]₀ = concentration of chelating agent in the organic layer, which gave *n* = 2.0, *m* = 1.0. Hence the stoichiometry of the extracted complex should be Pb(LCE)₃ (phen.). A similar β -diketo complex of lead has been reported earlier⁶.

Phosphor bronze which contains 1.31% phosphorus in the matrix, demands separation of lead before estimation by AAS. In lead determination by AAS, H₃PO₄ and PO₄³⁻ always cause interference and involves a lengthy separational procedure⁶. The present method is very simple and rapid in this respect. Nevertheless, gun metal and H.T. brass showed same results with or without separation.

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Extraction of Copper by Liquid Chelating Exchanger followed by its AAS Determination

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THE present communication reports the use of a β -diketo liquid chelating exchanger¹, RCOCH₂-COCH₃ (LCE) for extraction of copper and its determination by AAS. The method has been applied for the determination of copper in human blood samples.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. pH values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH meter. CuSO₄.5H₂O (E.Merck, G.R.) was used for the preparation of stock copper(II) solution.

Liquid chelating exchanger : Versatic-10 (C₁₀-isomeric monocarboxylic acid, Shell Chemical Co., London) was distilled and the exchanger was prepared in two steps. Versatic-10 was mixed with large excess of absolute ethanol and a little concentrated H₂SO₄, and the mixture was refluxed for 24 h. Ethyl ester thus produced was separated and purified by distillation. The resulting ester was then condensed with large excess of pure acetone in presence of sodium ethoxide by refluxing the mixture for 24 h. The resulting liquid β -diketo compound was separated and purified.

Procedure : To an aliquot (1.0 ml) of Cu^{II} solution containing 50 μg of the metal, dilute ammonia solution was added to adjust the pH to 8.0 and the mixture was transferred to a 50 ml separatory funnel. The tris-buffer (2 ml; pH 8.0) and 2.2×10^{-4} *M* LCE in chloroform (10 ml) was added to it and the mixture was shaken and allowed to settle. The organic layer was separated and any trace of organic phase associated with the aqueous layer was washed with chloroform (2 \times 5 ml) and mixed with the organic layer. The organic layer was then stripped with 0.05 *M* HCl (5 ml), and the

volume was made up to 10 ml with double-distilled water. This solution was aspirated to AAS and the amount of copper was determined from the calibration curve. The method was applied for the determination of copper in different blood samples (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN HUMAN BLOOD SAMPLES

Sample no.	Copper, $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	
	Direct aspiration	Proposed method
1	10.0	1.60
2	4.5	1.29
3	4.5	1.29
4	1.6	0.80
5	2.0	0.96
6	2.4	1.12

Results and Discussion

Copper was quantitatively extracted in the pH range 7.0–8.5. The quantitative extraction of copper mostly occurs with benzene, chloroform, cyclohexane and toluene, the extraction being 100%. Copper has been completely stripped back from organic layer to aqueous layer containing 0.03–3.00 *N* HCl. A shaking period of 1 min for extraction and a shaking period of 15 s for back-extraction have been found to be enough. On the other hand, 2 min were allowed for settling the equilibrium in case of extraction or back-extraction. Extraction of 50 ppm copper was increased with exchanger concentration and was complete at 1.6×10^{-3} mM. It has been found that the calibration curve of copper obtained by the general procedure is linear over the range 0.5–9.0 ppm. The stoichiometry of the extracted species has been found to be $\text{Cu}(\text{LCE})_2$.

Separation of copper from diverse ions: The extraction of a definite amount of copper (5 ppm) in presence of various ions (amount in parenthesis in ppm) was examined under experimental condition within an error of $\pm 2\%$ and the results are as follows: Na^+ , K^+ (8000); Li^+ (5000); Rb^+ , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} (2000); Ca^{2+} (1800); Cs^+ (1500); Ag^+ (350); Sn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} (50); Fe^{3+} (20); Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} (10); Mn^{2+} (8); Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} (6); Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} (5); large amounts of F^- , Cl^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , CrO_4^{2-} , MoO_4^{2-} do not interfere. The method was actually tested for copper extraction in the following synthetic mixtures (amount in parenthesis in ppm): (a) Li^+ , MoO_4^{2-} (1000); (b) Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} (5); (c) Mn^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} (5); (d) Mg^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} (5); (e) Ag^+ , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} (50).

In case of direct aspiration of the sample solution to AAS, high values for copper were obtained due to interference of large amounts of iron² and sodium⁸ present in blood (Table 1). The efficiency of the method in releasing copper from blood was

assessed by adding known amounts of copper to untreated blood samples, wet ashing them and determining the recoveries (97.5–102.5%) of the analyte.

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Inhibition of Corrosion of Mild Steel in Aqueous Solution of Chloride by Chromate†

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METALS when immersed completely in water tend to corrode because of their thermodynamic instability^{1–3}. Chloride, sulphate and nitrate ions are particularly aggressive. Sanyal and Nigam⁴ reported corrosion of mild steel in alcohol solution. Best and Roche⁵ investigated the use of chromate as inhibitor for ethanol, methanol, isopropanol and ethylene glycol. Chromate has been used effectively as inhibitor⁶ for brass in cooling water system. Sanyal and Grover⁷ showed that sodium nitrite and sodium chromate can be used as inhibitors for mild steel in water mains at 40°.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the corrosion of mild steel and the influence of chromate on it.

Experimental

Metal specimens, their preparation, the methods of measurement of corrosion rate, potential, percent-

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